

BEYOND THE ACT: UNDERSTANDING RAPE PERCEPTION AMONG STAKEHOLDERS IN NIGERIAN UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract: Rape, defined as the crime of forcing somebody to have sex, encompasses a spectrum of violent, destructive, and abusive behaviors, representing a blatant violation of an individual's self-worth, sense of security, and fundamental human dignity. This study delves into the intricate dimensions of rape, focusing on its various manifestations in today's interconnected global society. The literature on rape predominantly highlights its violent criminal aspects, revealing the multifaceted ways in which such incidents unfold within contemporary social networks. Throughout history, rape has been characterized by varying degrees of violence, often resulting in significant harm to the victim. Notably, the term 'rape' goes beyond its legal definition, encapsulating a broader violation of personal integrity and well-being. A pivotal aspect explored in this study is the marital dimension of rape, as identified by Riggs, Kilpatrick, and Reiss (1992) in their examination of marital rape and aggravated assault. The research underscores the influence of marital relationships as a potent causal factor in rape incidents. Their findings reveal that women subjected to assault by their husbands are more likely to report recurring attacks, suggesting a pattern of violence within marital dynamics. Furthermore, victims of aggravated assault, as compared to rape victims, are reported to express a heightened fear for their lives during the assault, shedding light on the distinct characteristics and psychological impact associated with different forms of interpersonal violence. This research aims to contribute to a deeper understanding of the complexities surrounding rape incidents, emphasizing the need for nuanced perspectives that go beyond legal definitions. By unraveling the layers of violence and exploring the specific dynamics within marital relationships, the study seeks to inform interventions and support systems tailored to the diverse experiences of survivors. Ultimately, this exploration contributes to the ongoing discourse on addressing and preventing rape, promoting a comprehensive approach that considers the psychological, relational, and societal implications of this heinous crime.

Keywords: Rape, Marital Dimension, Violence, Aggravated Assault, Victim Experiences

INTRODUCTION

The Nature of Rape

Rape is defined in the Encarta Web Dictionary variously as (a) the crime of forcing somebody to have sex, (b) violent, destructive, or abusive treatment of something and (c) as an act of seizing somebody and carrying her away by force (archaic). In its ordinary and legal usage, the word 'rape' connotes a flagrant violation of the victim's self worth, sense of security and the core essence of human dignity. There is a large body of literature that focuses attention on the various violent criminal dimensions which rape incidents have assumed in today's

global social networking. Indeed, rape has always been characterized by violence of various types, often carrying with it varying degrees of injury inflicted on the victim. In their study of marital rape and aggravated assault, Riggs, Kilpatrick, and Reisnick (1992) identified a marital dimension as a potent causal factor of rape. The study reported that women assaulted by their husbands were more likely to report that the assault was one of a series of similar attacks while victims of aggravated assault were reported to be more likely than rape victims to report that they feared for their lives during the assault. Battered women in shelter, according to Kemp, Rawlings, and Green (1991), were reported to suffer significantly from Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD). Just as Black et al. (1999) found that physical abuse by spouse was found to occur in 20 (18%) of the 111 women who had ever lived in a relationship, and sexual abuse in 19 (17%). Eleven (10%) had experienced both physical and sexual abuse. A history of physical abuse with or without sexual abuse by spouse was associated with sexual problems in the present or in previous relationships. Reported abuse by spouse was also associated with a higher frequency of gynaecological symptoms and that prior sexual victimization is a risk factor for partner sexual aggression. Russo, (2000) did agonize over the fact that despite an increasing awareness of the problem of sexual violence, there is still reluctance for date rape to be considered criminal or even unacceptable behaviour. Her work provided an overview of date rape, including what is known of its occurrence, the involvement of alcohol and drugs such as rohypnol, why it is a hidden crime, its impact on victims, and responses to it, including prevention strategies. In another insightful work, Groth, (1979) described four types of deliberate rapists, based on their motivations and behavior patterns. The categorization includes; the ‘power-assertive rapist’ argued to be the most common type of rapist, accounting for about 40 percent of all reported rapes. He tends to value physical aggression, he will commit date rape against victims he meets in places like bars, but he may pose as or be an authority figure. Power-assertive rapists do not intend to kill their victims, but to traumatize and humiliate them. They rarely target specific people for rape. There is also the ‘powerreassurance rapist’ who is usually socially deficient and unable to develop interpersonal or romantic relationships. They often fantasize about consensual sexual relationships with women, rather than violent conquest. The ‘Anger-retaliatory rapist’: on the other hand, is responsible for about 28% of rapes, this type of individual is often a substance abuser with impulsive behavior and angerrelated pathologies. The last categorization is ‘the angerexcitation rapist’. He is considered the most dangerous and elusive, accounts for about 4.5 percent of rapes. The anger-excitation rapist exhibits behavior characteristic of antisocial personality disorder, and is therefore, often perceived as charming and intelligent. Often sadistic, he will often torture or murder his victim to prevent her from identifying him, or for his own sexual gratification. In another study, Koss et al. (1985) identified that a social control/social conflict may explain what they termed a nonstranger sexual aggression while Poppen and Segal (1988), showed that males are far more likely than females to initiate coerced sexual behavior and females are more likely to be victimized. In addition, masculine persons reported using coercive strategies more than other sex role orientation types. Contradistinctively, Dietz and Jansinzi (2003) hypothesized that women who endorse more masculine traits will report higher perpetration of violence. Results of the study, however, demonstrate that the relationships between masculine and feminine traits and psychological abuse and physical assault are more complex than hypothesized.

The Nigerian Experience

Rape is a social malaise that conveniently finds its place among a long list of undesirable discrepant social behaviours that a developing economy like that of Nigeria has to contend with, but one hopes that with sustained public enlightenment and free but compulsory basic education at the primary education level, coupled with increased research into sundry variables that pertain to rape offenses, further escalation of rape incidents would be curtailed in due course of time. However, rape as a concept has a cultural connotation that gives impetus to the way it is socially perceived. In most Nigerian traditional cultures, sexual infidelity is viewed as a serious infraction against the established community norm of morality, hence offenders are severely punished. Unfortunately though, the punishment often prescribed is skewed in favour of the male offender while the female victim is stigmatized forever with the possible consequences of being socially branded, divorced or neglected by the husband, where she is already married, sentenced to social ostracization that may deny her the opportunity of getting a suitor to marry where she is yet unmarried, or at times sentenced to death where the community is yet fastened to the hard core traditional ways of doing things.

It should be pointed out that a random observation lends support to the fact that a heavy occurrence of rape incidents takes place in the institutions of higher learning across the length of the country than is found in any stratum of the Nigerian society (Nigerian Guardian's Editorial Report, May, 4 2004). Several reasons have been implicated as being responsible for the sustenance and rapid spread of this perceived 'unafrikan' fad. Chief among them is the developmental age hierarchy of adolescence, post-adolescence, and early adulthood that gives character label to the victims and perpetrators alike. Random assumptions also support the fact that there is a psychological mindset common to this age category which is governed by the cliché: "*flaunt it if you have it*". In reality what is flaunted are the sexual flashpoints such as the breasts, the buttocks, the navels etc. Arising from this, a dressing regime considered culturally aberrant becomes a fad among female university youngsters. If pre-adult females are, therefore, accused of indecent dressing for whatever reason, it follows that a corollary logic justifies the fact that the tribe of virile male contemporaries whose social repertoires may not have developed beyond the use of force as an alternative to the tedium of persuasion in their attempt to foster a social relationship, may feel challenged to consider rape as an option. Other reasons include vagrancy, general rise in violence proneness occasioned by depersonalized upswing of global technological advancement, drug addiction, alcoholism, cultism, prostitution etc.

Psychological Factors Capable of Influencing Rape in Institutions of Higher Learning

Institutions of higher learning comprise a heavy clustering of learners, whose age bracket peaks at 24, considering that the age range of the learners approximately spans 16–32 years with few exceptions breaking the upper limit barrier. Individuals occupying this developmental age category are characterized by such behavioral scripts as significant spurt of energy, egocentrism, (Elkind 1977), social identity and autonomy needs, (Erikson, 1968) at times impressionable and imitative (Bandura, 1977) and essentially competitive.

Universities and other institutions of higher learning are designed in a manner that would provide a conducive environment where these attributes can be learned or if already learned, improved upon. Individual constituents of the learning environment engage in a very active social interaction that hardly recognizes any barrier, least of all, gender. A lot of mingling and milling around take place to the extent that social consciousness, which is equally a veritable attribute of this age grade, naturally predisposes them to taking interest in members of the

opposite sex. Apart from the classrooms that are marked as major milling centres, a lot of other social activities are encouraged and indeed do take place at recreation centres that dot the campus space, in the halls of residence, at social gatherings and any other available space that can easily be maneuvered for social conveniences. With these social activities come other attendant social behaviours that at times may altogether not be wholesome. Such behaviours as these may include, as a result of the global sexual emancipation, active sexual relationship not enacted for reasons of reproduction. With this comes such consequences as frequent abortions, risk of contracting sexually transmitted diseases, frequent violent fights between estranged lovers, cult rivalries, ingestion of hard substances for social lifts, cigarette smoking, and because the entire length and breadth of the campus is theirs to explore, female learners equally lay claim to freedom of movement both during the day and at nights, again, often not without its dastardly consequences, such as rape, or other forms of sexual violence that find easy victim in them. It is indeed sad that accurate records of sexual violence on the campuses of Nigerian higher institutions are not available, because most incidents go unreported, and when reported at all, are not prosecuted for fear that it would inflict a permanent social scar on the victim to the extent of robbing him the gains of education. Since rape is a universal experience, some records obtained from the West will be highlighted. It was reported, quoting the US Justice Department (downloaded from <http://www.rainn.org/collegerape.htm> (2005)) rape record file that 1.7% of college women were victims of completed rape, and in 90% of the cases, the attacker was known to the victim. However, the study also found that in "about half of the incidents categorized as completed rapes, the women did not consider the incident to be a rape. Also, reported by, Briskin et al. (2005) in the Journal of Counseling and Development, women aged 16–24 are at the highest risk of sexual assault. Alcohol and drugs are implicated as playing a major role in rapes on college campuses in the U.S. According to "Alcohol and Sexual Assault on Campus" (*Administrator*, June 23, 2004), schools that have a record of heavy drinking have a 50-83% increased likelihood of assault.

The level of drinking is defined as women consuming four or more drinks consistently and five for men. Women under the age of twenty-one are 50% more likely to experience alcohol-related assaults. About 90% of rapes are allegedly planned. Date-rape drugs, or "roofies," such as flunitrazepam are occasionally used. They are quick to dissolve in drinks, and have no color, taste, or smell. Most have powerful sedative effects and can incapacitate the victim within 20–30 min of ingestion. They can also cause amnesia. In 2000, Congress enacted the Campus Sex Crimes Prevention Act which requires registered sex offenders working or studying at higher education institutes to notify the state. The Act further requires this information be made known to law enforcement agencies with jurisdiction over the institute of higher learning. Other Acts similar to this one have been put into effect in different states in order to prevent sex crimes from occurring on campus.

- What is rape? Is rape as a concept, considered a crime by participants?
- Is rape a more common phenomenon on Nigerian University campuses in the last ten years than it was in previous years? If yes, to what degree is it common?
- What causative factors can be held responsible for its occurrence? How is it perpetrated?
- Is the introduction of dressing code for female students alone an effective palliative measure for curbing rape incidents on campuses?

- What measure/s can be considered appropriate? With the foregoing as a guide, the study shall adopt the following methodology to achieve its aim;

Methodology

Cross-sectional survey method was adopted in sampling participants' opinions, while both quantitatively and qualitatively designed questionnaire (tagged Rape Evaluation Measure REM) was used as the technique of data gathering. REM comprised of 35 quantifiable response question items and three open ended questions. The measure was designed to assess participants' general perception of Rape incidents on Campus, determine what rape is and whether as a concept it can pass as a crime when committed, its prevalence, its aetiology, the methods used in perpetrating it, and the perceived palliative measures likely to curb its spread. The measure, outside other necessary biodata such as the sex, class level, age, marital status and the religious affiliation of participants, has five structural components designed to tap responses that would account for participants' opinion on the subject matter of rape. Statements that tally or fairly approximate the type participants have used to describe how they feel about rape incidents on campus were presented using the Likert (1932).

Sample: A total of 1500 questionnaires were randomly administered on stratified convenience participants in three Nigerian Universities drawn from each of the three regional divides of the country, namely the western, northern and Eastern geographical zones of the country. Data analysis was based on the data provided by 1455 questionnaires which constituted the validly returned participants' responses. Of this number, 798 were male, while 657 were female. Age range was 17 – 58, thus putting the age average at 32 years.

Suitability of the Instrument: The questionnaire was made available to colleagues with expertise in psychological measurement in the faculty of Social Sciences and other cognate faculties for scrutiny and to comment on the content validity. Their input shaped the present form of the questionnaire. A criterion validity check was done by running a correlating the score of selected 80 pilot participants on their understanding of the concept of rape as an expression of abnormal sex behaviour with the score rating drawn from their ability to describe actual behaviours (criterion) that constitute rape in its modern day context. The scores from the two tests correlate significantly at $r = 0.81$. For internal consistency, the arrangement and the weighting of the question items were not all made unidirectional, but intermittently arranged in opposite directions so as to forestall the possibility of casual responses. Where such is the case, it becomes easy to detect and therefore excluded from being part of the overall data. For reliability, both the split – half reliability method ($r = 0.72$) and 4 - week test-retest method ($r = 0.66$) confirmed the reliability of the test instrument. Also the language of the questionnaire tallied with the average proficiency expected of a person to whom English is a second language, which describes most of the participants. They expectedly would not suffer any serious comprehension problem granted the simple nature of the questions and the fact of their being mainly university undergraduates.

RESULT

The collation and analysis of the scores returned for the first nine question items of the questionnaire by participants were designed to be responsible for providing answer(s) to the first research question that seeks to know what participants' evaluation of rape as a form of sex behaviour is. That is, whether it could be construed as a crime or not and if a crime, what makes it a crime? In simple percentages, 60.3% of the 1452 who responded to the question that seeks to know whether rape occurs when force is used to subdue the opposite gender to have

sex strongly agree with the statement, while 30.1% agree. The addition of the number that disagree and strongly disagree came to 7%. To check for the consistency value of this response, the next question can only be answered in the negative for any level of consistent agreement with the first answer to be established. 56.7% and 25.0% participants strongly disagree (SD) and disagree (D) respectively with the statement which claims that rape occurs only when the woman is not paid the agreed sum of money after sex. Participants (52.6% SD, and 32.0% D) did not also agree with the statement that when a woman is not sexually satisfied after intercourse is when rape could be said to have occurred. Surprisingly, participants (12.65 SD, 33.2% D & 31.5% A, 13.6% SA, N = 1455) seemed sharply divided on the assumption that male gender also fall victim of rape as regularly as females. They were however quite clear on what makes rape a crime, for example; participants significantly agree (52.8% SA, 32.2 A) that rape is considered a crime first because the victim essentially suffers personal indignities, second, (35.5% A, 30.7% SA) that rape is a crime as it does not allow the victim any exercise of fundamental human right in the matter, and third (29.5% A, 36.3% SA) that rape is a crime essentially because it does often lead to unwanted pregnancy and the risk of contracting HIV/AIDS by the victim. From the foregoing the first research question is satisfactorily answered. However, the responses have level differentials, such as class, age, faith, marital status etc. to them. For example, using Pearson Moment Product correlation statistics, there was no significant correlation between the responses given and participants' age differentials ($r = 0.433$ $p > 0.05$). Using independent samples test to compare the scores of male and female participants on the concept of rape, a significant relationship existed ($t = -2.238$, $p < 0.05$ $df = 1405$). When the score of married and single participants were compared, no significant difference existed ($t = 1.618$ $p > 0.05$, $df = 1408$) as opposed to a significant difference which was found in the scores of participants when their scores were checked against their faith differentials ($F = 2.903$ $p < 0.05$ $df = 1409$). However at the level of educational status, a significant difference existed in the score of participants ($F = 3.047$ $p < 0.05$, $df = 1412$). (For graphic details. Table 1, Appendix 1). The prevalence rate of rape incidence on Nigerian university campuses prompted the second research question. Four question items were designed for the purpose of teasing out responses from participants in this regard. The following results were recorded in respect of each question; very high, like 3 victims in every 20 female students (9.70% SD, 21.2% D; 10.3% A, 28.2% SA with 26.0% Neutral, N = 1431). Moderately high, like 2 victims in every 20 female students (11.3% SD, 24.9% D, 24.5 A, 8.0% SA, 29.9 Neutral, N = 1449). Low, like 1 victim in every twenty female students (14.4% SD, 23.7% D 23.7%, 24.9% A, 9.7% SA, Neutral 24.5%, N = 1443). Does not exist at all in Nigerian university campuses

Table 1. Simple Percentage of Participants' Response Profile on Factors Responsible for Rape Incident on Campus.

Factors	Response Options	Frequency	%
Rape is committed by offenders that are slightly emotionally unstable	S. D.	156	10.8
	Disagree	309 186	21.2 12.8
	Neutral	540 234	37.1
	Agree** S. A.	1425	16.1
	N		

	S. D.	150	10.4
Rape is committed by offenders who suffer from fairly serious emotional problems	Disagree Neutral Agree** S. A. N S. D.	435 216 477 156 1434 138	30.1 14.8 32.8 10.7 9.5
Rape is committed by offenders who are acutely or seriously emotionally unstable	Disagree Neutral Agree** S. A. N S. D.	303 207 522 273 1443 216	20.8 14.2 35.9 18.8 14.9
Rape is committed by individuals who have been made lawless by campus life	Disagree** Neutral Agree S. A. N S.D.	420 270 330 201 1437 219	29 18.7 22.8 13.8 15.3
Rape is committed because there is a general laxity in the rules that govern conduct on Nigerian University Campus	Disagree** Neutral Agree S. A. N S. D.	444 207 375 153 1398 81	31.1 14.5 25.8 10.5 5.6
General breakdown in moral values in the society has percolated to the campuses therefore causing offenders to commit rape	Disagree Neutral Agree** S. A. N S. D. Disagree	228 144 642 300 1395 72 39	15.7 9.9 44.1 20.6 4.9 2.7
Indecent dressing by female students encourages rape on campus.	Neutral Agree** S. A. N S. D.	36 540 738 1425 186	2.5 37.1 50.7 12.8
Indecent dressing has little to do with rape. Offenders will rape, indecent dressing or not	Disagree Neutral Agree** S. A. N	336 150 531 189 1398	23.1 10.3 36.5 13

Table 1. Contd.

Factors	Response Options	Frequency	%
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Offenders do commit rape because girls on campus play hard to get	S. D.	348	23.9
	Disagree**	537	36.9
	Neutral	270	18.6
	Agree S. A. N	195	13.4
	S. D.	69	4.7
	Disagree**	1419	
		297	20.4
Rape is committed because students are becoming more antisocial as a result of global advanced technology		426	29.7
	Neutral	225	15.7
	Agree S. A.	345 129	23.7
	N	1422	8.9
Rape victims are attacked because they make rapists feel insecure as a result of their display of false sophistication.	S. D.	186	12.8
	Disagree**	405	27.8
	Neutral	408	28
	Agree S. A. N	306	21.5
	S. D.	99	6.8
		1404	
		105	7.2
Offenders do commit rape so as to punish victims considered arrogant	Disagree	357	24.5
	Neutral	273	18.8
	Agree**	561	38.6
	S. A. N	126	8.7
	S. D.	1422	
		120	8.2
		264	18.1
Excessive alcohol consumption encourages offenders to commit rape	Disagree	264	18.1
	Neutral	150	10.3
	Agree** S. A.	627 258	43.1 17.7
	N	1419	
A high rate of rape crime on campuses can be blamed on free use of drug by potential offenders	S. D.	114	7.8
	Disagree	339	23.3
	Neutral	279	19.2
	Agree** S. A. N	543 141	37.3 9.7
	S. D.	1414	
		276	19
	Disagree**	486	33.4

The frustrating economic downturn in Nigeria encourages rape incidents on campus	Neutral Agree S. A. N	279 297 78 1416	19.2 20.4 5.4
Uncensored access to pornographic movies by students is the chief cause of rape on campus	S. D. Disagree Neutral Agree** S. A. N	45 264 174 621 306 1410	3.1 18.1 12 42.7 21

SD - Strongly Disagree SA - Strongly Agree

** - considered the voice of participants based on simple majority after adding the two gradients on each divide e.g. SD + D or A + S

Table 2. Participants' perception of techniques commonly adopted by rapists.

Techniques	Response Classifications	Score	%
Rapists target newly admitted students who are naïve about life on campus	S. D. Disagree Neutral Agree** S. A. N	129 348 303 483 150 1413	8.9 23.9 20.8 33.2 10.5
Rape victims are tricked into the ordeal with the promise of money	S. D. Disagree** Neutral Agree S. A. N	276 483 234 339 75 1407	19.0 33.2 16.1 23.3 5.2
A girl cannot be too smart when she is marked out by rapist	S. D. Disagree Neutral Agree** S. A. N	84 258 168 633 255 1398	5.8 17.7 11.5 43.5 17.5
Rape is never a planned crime, rapists pounce on their victims wherever and whenever the opportunity avails itself	S. D. Disagree** Neutral Agree S. A. N	153 468 192 390 207 1410	10.5 32.2 13.2 26.8 14.2

Rape is carefully planned and carried out with precision	S. D.	66	4.5
	Disagree	234	16.1 13.8
	Neutral	201 648	44.5 17.8
	Agree** S. A.	252	
	N	1401	

Strongly Disagree SA - Strongly Agree

** - considered the voice of participants based on simple majority after adding the two gradients on each divide e.g. SD + D or A +

SA

(61.9% SD, 20.0% D, 3.5% A, 10.9% SA, Neutral 3.1%, N = 1452). The foregoing response analysis does not cut a decisive picture of what the rate of occurrence might be since no significant agreement appears to have been reached by participants regarding the assumed rate of occurrence. What was however confirmed was the fact that rape incidents definitely occur on Nigerian university campuses given the fact that altogether, about 80% of the participants strongly disagree and disagree respectively with the suggestion that rape does not exist on Nigerian university campuses. Male and female participants appear sharply divided on the issue of rate of occurrence as a significant difference exists in their response profile ($t = -4.355$, $p < .05$; df 1420). Whereas no significant difference exists in the response of married and single participants ($t = .468$, $p > .05$, df 1423). When the responses to the same issue of the occurrence of rape on campus were analyzed according to the faith dimensions of participants, significant differences existed ($F = 2.833$, $p < .05$, df 1424) but did not exist when analyzed according to educational status ($F = 1.643$, $p > 0.05$). The third research question seeks to know what causative factors can be held responsible for the occurrence of rape incidents on Nigerian university on Nigerian university campuses. Male and female participants appear sharply divided on the issue of rate of into a multiple of 16 questions believed to cover the different factorial dimensions. The 16 question items shown in Table 1 to which participants were significantly in agreement, can be arranged around four major factors, namely a] behavior deficit arising from biological imbalance such as These dimensions and participants' responses are presented in Table 1; indulgence

3 Pe ceptions on Causative Factors of Rape According to Levels.

Levels	Dimensions	N	Mean	SD	t	df	Sig.
Sex	Male	738	50.7	7.20	-2.71	1351	.007**
	Female	615	51.8	7.31			
Marital Status	Married	90	50.5	8.30	-1.18	1354	.236
	Single	1320	51.3	7.12			
Religion	Christianity	882	51.3	6.99	F	3	.002**
	Islam	171	51.1	6.96			
	Traditional	84	53.5	7.67			
Educational Level	Part One	1194	51.18	7.15	1.87	1353	.096
	Part two	33	54.72	6.99			
	Part Three	30	51.20	8.85			
	Part Four	30	51.30	6.92			
	Masters	0	0000	000			
	Ph.D	3	56.00	8.12			

** Significant at the 0.05 level (2 – tailed)

in drug ingestion or psychiatric problem, b] laxity in the rules that govern conduct on university campuses, c] break down in societal values both at the local and global levels and d] aberrative behavioural disposition of both the victims and the offenders. In the first category, an overwhelming agreement appears to characterize participants' response. This translates to mean that participants perceive rape to be a form of an aberrant behaviour that must necessarily have a basis in a kind of mental illness to justify the dastardly act in the mind of the offender. The second category of questions which essentially call to question the rules that govern good moral conduct on campuses also received an overwhelming 'aye' from participants. Whereas they were not in total agreement with some suggestions made about certain personal beliefs of victims and offenders as being solely responsible for the occurrence of rape on campus. However participants were in agreement with the suggestion that the break down in societal values both at the local and global level need be implicated as capable of precipitating rape incidents on campus. The following tables depict participants' responses to the suggested techniques commonly adopted by rapist on campus. From Table 2, four clear sets of consensus emerged namely that; i) part of the technique common to rapists is that they target newly admitted students who are naïve about life on campus, ii) money does not necessarily feature as part of the tool of allurements in rape perpetration, iii) being smart does not necessarily absolve any female student from attack from rapists, iv] rape is campus. Female participants are found to record a marginally stronger feeling about the variables. Similarly a significant difference existed in the perception of the various religious groups with the traditionalists expressing a fairly stronger feeling about the focal variable. In Table 4, participants' perception about the techniques constantly adopted by rapist in the pursuit of the aberrant behaviour, rape is graphically presented. In Table 3, a significant difference existed between the perception of male and female participants on the techniques adopted by rapists in perpetrating rape. This difference was however in degrees of intensity of feeling and not in perceptual divergence. In Table 4, evidences abound in support of conceptual concordance among participants about the techniques constantly adopted by rapists. The difference, however, tilts in favour of female participants. Similarly, a significant difference existed in the perception of married and single participants in terms of strong expression of feelings about the focal variable, though in the same perceptual direction. Married participants felt more strongly about the techniques used. The research was also interested in sounding participants out on what in their opinion (using openended question format) is the major reason why rape is committed on the campuses of Nigerian tertiary institutions, and the corollary; what measures can be considered appropriate for curbing a possible escalation of rape incidents on campus. Participants' response profile on this two question teasers are presented in tables 5 and 6. The opinion of participants as it appears in Table 5

carefully planned and carried out with precision. comes out clearly without ambiguity, i.e. if the highest

More details of the spread of participants' responses opinion frequency is to be reckoned with. This appears to according to level when responses on causative factors have answered the main crux of the research question and techniques adopted by rapists are examined will be and question 4 in particular. However, Table 6, presented shown in the Tables 3 and 4. below will highlight what participants think the palliative

A significant difference existed between the perception measures for curbing rape incidents on campus should of female participants and their male counterparts on be.

what factors are responsible for rape incidents on

4 Perception, According to Levels, about the Techniques Constantly Adopted by Rapists.

Levels	Dimensions	N	Mean	SD	t	df	Sig.		
Sex	Male	762 618	18.17	3.35	-2.31	1378	0.021**		
	Female		18.60	3.42					
Marital Status	Married	87 1299	19.06 18.32	3.77	1.97	1384	0.048**		
	Single			3.36					
Religion	Christianity	906 171		3.37	F	3	0.159		
	Islam	84	18.2	3.20				1.75	1379
	Traditional		3	3.67					1382
Educational Level	Part One	1206 33		3.35	2.169	6	0.44		
	Part two	30	18.2	2.73				1379	
	Part	30	9	3.07				1385	
	Three Part		19.18	2.58					
	Four		18.80	.000					
	Masters Ph.D	3 3	18.40	.000					
			15.00						
			16.00						

** Significant at the 0.05 level (2 – tailed)

Table 5. Opinion Rating of Causative Factors of Rape on Campus

Factors	Frequency	%
Indecent dressing by female students	927	63.7**
Financial handicap	6	.4
High rate of cultic activities on campus	30	2.1
Lack of proper homegrown moral values in students	231	15.9
Fallout of advanced technology	18	1.2
Uncensored access to pornographic movies	39	2.7
Excessive consumption of alcoholic beverages by students	18	1.2
Lack of effective security measures on campus	15	1.0
Lack of proper student orientation to life on campus	24	1.6
General lack of discipline on campus and immaturity on the part of students	21	1.4

Academic stress combined with transferred antisocial life	9	.6
Total	1338	92.0
Missing Cases	117	8.0
Grand Total	1445	100

** Significant to represent the opinion of participants

Finding a way of stopping the wearing of indecent by a combination of drives which can be located in the id dressing by female students, and the need to introduce region of Freudian personality classifications. Id, dress code for students on campus appear to be the valid according to Freud, (1964b) is the reservoir of the suggestion of participants for curbing the continued instinctual drives of the individual biological urges, perpetration of rape on campus (Table 6). wishes, and affective motives. The id is dominated by the pleasure principle, through which the individual is pressed for immediate gratification of desires. According to the theory of Sigmund Freud, the energy behind the This study, through participants' responses, has been instinctual drives of the id is known as the libido-a able to shed light on the various questions advanced to generalized force which is basically sexual in nature guide the course of the investigations carried out in this through which the sexual and psychosexual nature of the study. For example; rape as a form of human behaviour individual finds expression. The findings in this study is associated with violence, criminal conduct, antisocial confirm that while rape is not condoned socially, it is inclination and flagrant violation of fundamental human equally seen as a culturally aberrant behaviour. right. It is seen as one behaviour script whose emission Rape incident is considered a common phenomenon in whatever form is not socially desirable, hence has no on Nigerian University campuses, even though place in civilized communalism. What justifies the participants were somewhat ambivalent about the actual negative and antisocial label attached to individuals who rate of occurrence. This finding does not come as a indulge in rape is that the behaviour is in itself motivated surprise, particularly, to close watchers of social activities 6 Cu bing Rape Occurrence on Campuses.

Factor	Frequency	%
Adequate sensitization of students to the evil effect of rape	12	.8
Proper financial responsibility by parents	15	1.9
By finding a way of stopping the wearing of indecent dressing by female students	504	34.2**
By discouraging students from peering with bad gangs	3	.2
By embarking on proper sex education and social awareness	189	13.0
Girls should be discouraged from frequenting dark and lonely places	18	1.2
More religious activities should be encouraged on campus	48	3.3
Proper punishment should be meted out to rape offenders	195	13.4
Stop showing pornographic movies on campus	99	6.8
Introduce dress code for students on campus	207	14.2*
Girls should be discouraged from walking alone at night	15	1.0
Ensure adequate security on campus	60	4.1
Drinking of alcoholic drinks on campus should be banned	24	1.7
Total	1389	96.5
Missing cases	66	4.5
Grand Total	1455	100

*Valid **Significant to represent participants' approximate recommendation correspondence with the lead opinion as they play out on Nigerian university campuses. At regular intervals, rape incidents are contended with by the section of the university management that oversees students' affairs. The case report presented earlier in this paper was a fallout from a similar occurrence. Several factors were fingered as likely to be responsible for rape perpetration on university campuses. Chief among them is the indecent dressing penchant of female students which is characterized by undue exposure of body parts considered sensual. Following in a descending order of strong expression of feeling are such factors as; breakdown of moral rectitude in the society which in a way has percolated to the university campuses, uncensored exposure of students to pornographic movies, excessive consumption of alcohol by students, cultic activities on campus coupled with techniques devised by devious antisocial villains to get back on girls they consider sophisticated and above their social level, actual use of hard drug, poor security arrangement on campus, lack of discipline and maturity, academic stress and advancement of technology. Participants disagree significantly in a descending degree of emotional expression with the following suggestions; that rape occur because girls play hard to get, that rape is induced by economic downturn that has afflicted the polity in recent times, and that rules and regulations are too relaxed on university campuses. The method of operation as was perceived by participants vary in the order of their importance to cover such techniques as ; that rapists do not just pounce on their victims but that they carefully plan and carry out their operation with precision, that newly admitted students, because of their seeming naivety and impressionable disposition, come handy as easiest targets. Also the idea that one can play smart and therefore avoid falling victim of rape did not go down well with participants as they express strong feelings in favor of the fact that, once marked out for rape, a girl could not be too smart to avoid what she has no previous knowledge of. Finally that money could be used and was often being used as a weapon to lure victims into rape ordeal was not a popular suggestion with participants. The palliative measures that could be put in place to stave off the continued perpetration of rape crime were proffered by participants and in the order of the level of the consensus presented through their responses, the following suggestions were offered; embark on concerted campaign that will effectively discourage the wearing of indecent dresses by students especially the female ones. This was followed by the suggestion that dress codes need be introduced so that the appearance of students on campus will synchronize with decency. Other suggestions range in the following order; serious punishments should be meted to rapists when they are caught, indeed, outright expulsion is not considered high handed if it would serve as a deterrent. Putting in place an elaborate sex education programme and social comportment awareness campaign, outright censorship of pornographic materials, especially, movies on campus; putting in place adequate security measures around the campus such that would permit proper monitoring of students' movement; encourage more religious activities which by its nature would boost moral upliftment of students on campus; drinking of alcoholic beverages and smoking should be banned on campus; girls should be discouraged through sustained information dissemination 50 from roaming spots considered unsafe alone whether at night or in the afternoon; parents be sensitized to the need to provide adequate means of sustenance for their wards on campus and finally that the existence of dangerous gangs on campus must be made a nullity.

CONCLUSION

Even though some of these suggestions may be difficult to effect given the peculiar nature of a university establishment and environment, they represent the genuine feelings of the participants, and indeed succeeded effectively to provide a decisive answer to the major question raised in the study which requires an answer to whether rape is in the eye of the offender. Indecent dressing that leaves exposed a revealing part of the woman's breast, waist and navel, backside (upper & lower), the frontal region above the thighs (the pubic region and

environment) and the thigh, is capable of creating impressions that may trigger basal instincts in crime prone personalities hence the unprecedented high rise in rape crime. The new trend of indecent dressing among youths in Nigeria, particularly, among university female undergraduates, was rightly brought into the front burner as a result of its explosive potentials. However, it soothes the mind to know that some universities have considered the issue serious enough to outrightly legislate against it, and as a panacea, reel out series of codes of conduct on dressing so as to checkmate indecent appearance of scholars on campus. The university being a mill where manpower is manufactured and manpower by extension being the bulwark of every virile economy. It therefore appeals to reason to imagine the university and its products as integral to the networking that provides for the society its self sustaining mechanism, without which anarchy and chaos will be the reward to be reaped by the society.

Recommendation

Justifications have been devised for the actions taken by some of the universities in addressing the issue of indecent dressing in the premises of a learning establishment. Prominent among such justifications is the fact that a university should have a distinguishing hallmark unique enough in its essence to set it apart from, say, the assemblage of touts, prostitutes, rascals, and the untutored. Also, that decency should characterize conduct in an environment marked as a citadel of learning. That indecent dressing is an evil prompt that galvanizes the idea of rape in the mind of rapists. Sound as these arguments may appear, they leave unanswered certain pertinent questions, some of which have been answered in this study. Attention is however hereby pointed to others that are yet to be answered but have the potentials to precipitate other research studies.

The questions cover such salient factors as, for example, the issue of alcohol consumption in and around university campuses. In line with the suggestions proffered in a study carried out by Mohler-Kuo et al. (2004). There is a pertinent suggestion in the direction that there is the need for alcohol prevention programs to be put in place on campuses, which will address sexual assault, and will be further designed both to educate men about what constitutes rape and to advise women of risky situations. Other areas of attention also include giving a thought to introducing intervention programmes that will address the need to help restore the confidence, composure and dignity of victims, probably in line with the works of Koss et al. (2004). Other questions to be considered include; are there categorical evolutionary trends in dressing mode among Nigerian youths in the past two decades or more? If there is, what characterized the nature of these changes i.e. was it rapid, or gradual, adapted, or adopted, resisted or encouraged etc. Another pertinent question is, how much of the new trend is a product of the myriad social problems already in contention before this new development. It should be noted that there was undue sexual emancipation, prostitution even among university undergraduates, drug addiction, cultism, vandalism, armed robbery, ritual murder and a host of other social problems to which attention also need be paid. A more holistic approach to analyzing, categorizing and classifying these problems so as to proffer sustainable solution is recommended.

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